

TABLE 2—THE η_{sp}/c AND D COEFFICIENT VALUES FOR GLYCINE AT 308.15 K IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	$B/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$D/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-2}$
5% methanol	0.164	0.0947
15% methanol	0.207	0.0545
25% methanol	0.173	0.1700
5% ethanol	0.168	0.1702
15% ethanol	0.182	0.0645
25% ethanol	0.192	0.0200
5% <i>n</i> -propanol	0.158	-0.0645
15% <i>n</i> -propanol	0.168	-0.1429
25% <i>n</i> -propanol	0.174	0.2143
5% <i>t</i> -butanol	0.126	0.3654
15% <i>t</i> -butanol	0.141	0.1290
25% <i>t</i> -butanol	0.157	-0.3529

attributed^{10,11} to the fact that addition of small amount of ethanol in water enhances the structure of water resulting in a more structured solvent. With this observation we shall assume that the increase in viscosity with addition of alcohol to water up to 25% w/w of alcohol is due to the successive enhancement of structure in the solvent mixtures.

(ii) In Table 2 the B coefficients of glycine show increase with increase in percentage of alcohol in the solvent mixtures. It is also known from previous studies² that glycine in water solutions having high B coefficients acts as a net structure breaker. Using the above description of glycine in water, the increase in B coefficients support the interpretation that glycine is even more effective as a structure breaker in alcohol-water mixtures than in water. The increased structure breaking by glycine in the mixed solvent is probably due to the already enhanced structure in the original solvent mixtures.

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Influence of Dipolar Aprotic Solvents on Micellization of Aqueous Solution of Surfactants. Part—I: A Study of Micellization of Surfactants in $\text{H}_2\text{O-N,N-Dimethyl Formamide}$ Solution

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MICELLIZATION studies in aquo-organic solvent systems have largely been restricted to protic solvents like alcohols and aprotic water soluble solvents like dioxane. Some workers have used acetone and various amides as cosolvents to study their effect on cmc's. McDonald¹ observed substantially higher values of cmc's for nonionic surfactants in formamide and lower values for some sodium carboxylates both in formamide and *N*-methyl acetamide. Gopal and coworkers²⁻⁴ reported aggregation of ionic surfactants in solvents having one hydrogen bonding centre, like *n*-methyl acetamide. This paper considers the effect of *N,N*-dimethyl formamide, a dipolar aprotic solvent having no hydrogen bonding centre, on the cmc's of CTAB, NaLS and Triton-X-100.

Experimental

N,N-Dimethyl formamide (DMF) was of spectrograde (E. Merck) and used without further purification. The surfactants used in this study were cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB), sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS), both of BDH make and used after purification⁵. Polyoxyethylene-9,5-diisobutyl phenol (Triton-X-100) was of BDH make and used without further purification. The dye used was methyl violet (E. Merck) [$\lambda_{\text{max}}=580$ nm and $\epsilon_{\text{max}}=25,000$]. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water and preserved in "Corning" glass apparatus in the dark to avoid any photochemical reaction, and used within 7 days of preparation.

All measurements were carried out spectroscopically using a Carl Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer containing thermostated cell holders. The solutions required for experiment were bottled and shaken thoroughly for 2 hr to ensure complete incorporation. The bottles were then kept in the thermostat for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr to attain temperature equilibrium. Change of optical densities were followed at the maximum absorption, of the dye i.e. at 580 nm in aqueous and mixed solvent systems, in varying concentrations of the surfactants, and at a fixed dye concentration (1×10^{-5} M). Each value reported is an average of 3 readings. From the plots of O. D. vs concentration of surfactant, the

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Fig. 1. Plot of optical density vs concentration of hexadecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide in presence of methyl violet in water-N,N-dimethyl formamide solution at 25°

critical micelle concentration of each set was determined. The break in the plot was taken as an indication of micelle formation and corresponds to the cmc. No micelle formation was assumed with linear plots.

The change in O.D. with concentration of CTAB was followed at two different temperatures, 25 and 40° and the thermodynamic parameters were calculated.

Results and Discussion

The optical density values of the solutions have been plotted against surfactant concentrations. In

CTAB, a sudden jump in the O.D. is obtained by the addition of surfactant, which then remains constant and subsequently decreases. The later break point has been taken as the cmc for the CTAB surfactant at different molefractions of DMF (Fig. 1). With NaLS and Triton-X-100 surfactants the curve follows a common pattern, i.e. the O.D. values first rise regularly and then remain almost constant (Figs. 2 and 3). In all cases the cmc values are higher than those in water. The change in the cmc with the change in the solvent composition in all the three surfactants are summarised in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Plot of optical density vs concentration of sodium lauryl sulphate in presence of methyl violet in water-N,N-dimethyl formamide solutions at 25° ; molefraction of DMF = 0.091

Fig. 3. Plot of optical density vs concentration of Triton-X-100 (in volume %) in presence of methyl violet in water-DMF solution at 25° ; molefraction of DMF = 0.025

TABLE 1—CRITICAL MICELLE CONCENTRATION OF SURFACTANTS AT DIFFERENT MOLEFRACTIONS OF DMF IN WATER-N,N-DIMETHYL FORMAMIDE SOLUTION

Percentage of DMF (v/v)	Molefraction of DMF	CMC at ^a 25° 10 ⁴ × M	CMC at ^b 40° 10 ⁴ × M	CMC at ^c 25° 10 ⁴ × M	CMC at 25 ^d in volume%
0	0.00	9.10	9.90	8.20	0.54
5	0.012	15.00	—	12.10	0.68
10	0.025	21.50	23.90	16.30	0.92
15	0.039	26.20	—	20.50	1.00
20	0.054	33.00	37.30	25.00	1.00
30	0.091	55.00	62.70	30.00	1.00
40	0.134	101.00	116.00	45.00	1.00
50	0.189	125.50	199.00	—	—
60	0.259	298.0	—	—	—
65	0.303	600.00	—	—	—
67.5	0.326	—	—	—	—
70	0.353	—	—	—	—

a=CTAB, b=CTAB, c=NaLS and d=Triton-X-100.

The cmc values increase with increasing molefraction of DMF, the rate of increase, however, is more pronounced in CTAB and less in NaLS and Triton-X-100. It has been rationalised that cmc's increase when the cosolvent is a structure breaker, i.e. when the strength of surfactant hydrophobic interaction is decreased. In Triton-X-100, the cmc values remain constant after a molefraction of 0.039 of DMF. However, formation of micelles does not appear at a molefraction of 0.134. In case of NaLS also a similar result is obtained. But in case of CTAB, formation of micelles does not appear to take place beyond a molefraction of 0.33 of DMF. The mixing of DMF with water is a strongly exothermic process with a maximum value at a molefraction of 0.34 for DMF⁸. A variety of other physical properties of H₂O-DMF mixtures exhibit maxima at a molefraction of 0.34 for DMF. Calorimetric and cryoscopic measurements have indicated the formation of DMF-H₂O and DMF-2H₂O species⁸, the association being ascribed to hydrogen bond formation.

In a solution containing 0.33 molefraction of DMF, water already has an ordered structure due to its association with DMF through hydrogen bonding. Addition of surfactant amphiphiles, therefore, does not bring in a greater order into the structure of water. So the entropy increase due to micellization, acting as a driving force for micellization no longer exists. Hence micelles are not formed.

Thermodynamics of micelle formation :

Thermodynamics of micelle formation has been treated extensively in literature⁹⁻¹¹. Assuming the phase separation model, Tanford¹² arrived at the equation (1) relating the change in free energy with cmc.

$$\Delta G_m^0 = RT \ln CMC \quad \dots (1)$$

Assuming that the aggregation number and the degree of ionisation of surfactant are independent of temperature, the standard enthalpy (ΔH_m^0) and

standard entropy (ΔS_m^0) of micellization are evaluated from the temperature dependence of cmc. The experimental results show that micelle formation is slightly shifted to a higher concentration of the surfactant by increasing the temperature from 25 to 40° (Table 1).

The ΔG_m^0 values change linearly with increasing molefraction of DMF and are always less negative than those determined in pure water. The approximate enthalpy of micellization is exothermic and almost constant at molefraction of DMF between 0.025 to 0.134. The corresponding values of entropy of micellization decrease gradually from +7.5 to +3.5 e.u. This indicates that the negative value of ΔG_m^0 is mainly due to the contribution of the entropy term in H₂O-DMF mixed solvent system at low molefractions of DMF. This is in agreement with the general concept that micelle formation in aqueous solution is entropy directed process.

The decrease in ΔS_m^0 values with increasing molefraction of DMF (Table 2) indicates an increase in the orderliness of the CTAB-H₂O-DMF system. This is consistent with a strong interaction such as hydrogen bonding between water and DMF.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMICS OF MICELLE FORMATION OF CTAB IN WATER-N,N-DIMETHYL FORMAMIDE SOLUTIONS

Molefraction of DMF	ΔH_m^0 K.cal.mole ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_m^0$ at 25° K.cal.mole ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_m^0$ at 40° K.cal.mole ⁻¹	ΔS_m^0 at 25° e.u.
0.00	—	4.1	4.3	—
0.025	-1.36	3.6	3.75	7.51
0.054	-1.38	3.33	3.47	6.4
0.091	-1.47	3.0	3.15	5.1
0.134	-1.65	2.7	2.77	3.5
0.189	-5.65	2.5	2.43	-10.5
0.259	—	2.0	—	—

Altogether, the inhibitory effect of DMF in micelle formation in H₂O-DMF mixed solvent system can be viewed in terms of a decrease in the hydrophobic interaction in ternary system due to the interaction between water and cosolvent.

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Oxidation of Carbon Monoxide over Perovskite-like-LaMn₂Co_{1-x}O₃ Catalysts

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MODERNIZATION has inevitably brought in pollution. In urban areas, motor vehicles account for probably more than 50% of pollutants like carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides. Thus, development of automotive exhaust catalysts has assumed importance. Recently, solid state chemistry is increasingly being brought to bear on the formulation of catalytic materials. Around 1970, cobaltite perovskites were suggested as substitutes for the costlier and rarer noble metals¹. Encouraging results were obtained with LaCoO₃ and LaMnO₃ in the oxidation of carbon monoxide and the reduction of nitric oxide^{2,3}. However, the feasibility of the mixed LaMnO₃-LaCoO₃ system has apparently not been investigated so far. In this article, the results of oxidation of carbon monoxide over these mixed catalysts are reported and discussed.

Experimental

Several samples with the nominal composition LaMn₂Co_{1-x}O₃, 0 ≤ x ≤ 1, were synthesized by heating appropriate mixture of oxalates of lanthanum, cobalt and manganese in an atmosphere of

oxygen at 900-1000° for several hours. Formation of single phase compounds with perovskite-like structure was confirmed through analysis of X-ray powder diffractogrammes using CuK_α (λ = 1.5418 Å).

Catalytic activity was determined in a flow reactor employing a feed gas of composition 5%CO, 5%O₂ and 90%N₂. Carbon monoxide was prepared by the dehydration of formic acid with conc. sulphuric acid. Commercial grade oxygen and nitrogen gas, supplied in cylinders by Indian Oxygen Ltd., Bombay were used. However, these gases were individually purified further by passing through various traps (like sodium hydroxide for the removal of carbon dioxide in carbon monoxide, heated copper turnings at 400° for the removal of oxygen in nitrogen, etc.) and each gas was then analysed, using gas chromatograph, to be of 99.9% pure. The individual gas flow rates were controlled by using flow-meters and needle valves and mixed in a glass bulb. The composition of the mixture was checked using the gas chromatograph before passing through the catalyst bed. The space velocities used were between 19,000-25,000 ml/h-ml of catalyst. The feed gas and the products were analyzed on an on-line gas chromatograph. The temperature range was between 200-350°.

Results and Discussion

The preparative conditions and the X-ray data of the compositions are given in Table 1. It can be noted that all the compositions belong to the rhombohedral system and that the unit cell volume increases regularly with increasing manganese content. The activation energy and the frequency factor for the oxidation of carbon monoxide is also summarised in Table 1. The variation of the rate of oxidation (R_i) with temperature is shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 2 depicts the variation of percentage conversion with temperature.

For pure LaMnO₃, the catalytic activity was negligible. For isothermal conditions, the activity increased with increasing cobalt content and only slightly after x ~ 0.4. The constancy of activation energy values indicates that the mechanism of catalytic action presumably remains the same. In general, the conversion corresponding to maximum

TABLE 1—STRUCTURAL AND KINETIC DATA FOR THE SYSTEM LaMn₂Co_{1-x}O₃

X	Preparative conditions		Rhombohedral lattice parameters			Activation energy E _a k cal.mole ⁻¹	Frequency factor A (S ⁻¹)
	Sintering temperature (°C)	Duration of sintering (days)	a (Å)	c (°)	v (Å ³)		
0.0	1000	4	7.665	90.5	450.25	19.70	2.24 × 10 ⁺⁸
0.3	1000	8	7.719	90.5	459.83	18.25	9.55 × 10 ⁺¹
0.5	1000	4	7.774	89.9	469.73	20.65	8.92 × 10 ⁺²
0.6	900	4	7.794	89.8	473.46	21.20	1.82 × 10 ⁺²

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